

GC-MS Analysis of Bioactive Compounds from Ethanolic Stem Extract of *Tinospora Cordifolia* and Their Pharmacological Activities

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ABSTRACT

Bioactive compounds serve as pivotal agents in both the nutraceutical and pharmaceutical sectors. Recently, these compounds have garnered significant attention due to their capacity to enhance resistance to various diseases and improve human health through both traditional and modern methods of administration. Consequently, the present study was conducted to identify the compounds present in the stem of *Tinospora cordifolia* using Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) analysis of an ethanol extract. The GC-MS analysis revealed the presence of 48 bioactive compounds. The primary compounds identified include n-Hexadecanoic acid, Z,Z-8,10-Hexadecadien-1-ol, Octadecanoic acid, tetracosane, 9-Octadecenoic acid (Z)-, 2,3-bis(acetyloxy)propyl ester, and beta-Sitosterol. Each compound was identified in the mass spectrum based on its retention time and peak area. The pharmacological activities of these compounds suggest that the constituents present in the stem of the mentioned plant can be utilized as a crude drug and hold potential for the development of novel pharmaceuticals.

Keywords: Bioactive compounds, Ethanolic stem extract, GC-MS, Pharmacological activity, *Tinospora cordifolia*.

INTRODUCTION

The pharmaceutical industry increasingly employs bioactive compounds as potent agents in the treatment of various diseases. Recently, these compounds have gained prominence due to their therapeutic potential. India possesses a rich heritage of medicinal plants, which have the capacity to synthesize organic compounds known as secondary metabolites. These metabolites, characterized by their unique and complex structures, are utilized in the treatment of both chronic and infectious diseases [1]. *Tinospora cordifolia* is a highly esteemed medicinal plant, recognized for its anti-diabetic, immunomodulatory, hepatoprotective, anti-mycobacterial, anti-cancer, anti-viral, anti-inflammatory, and neurological benefits, including the management of psychiatric conditions, Parkinson's disease, dementia, and motor and cognitive deficits [2,3], as well as its diuretic properties [4]. In recent years, Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) has emerged as a crucial tool for profiling secondary metabolites in

plants. However, there are limited reports available on the pharmacological properties of this plant. In light of this, the present study aims to establish the GC-MS profile of the ethanolic leaf extract of *Tinospora cordifolia* and investigate its pharmacological activities.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant material

Tinospora cordifolia Miers (Menispermaceae) (TC) were gathered from the Vidyabharti College, Seloo Dist. Wardha. The plant was identified and authenticated from Post Graduate Department of Botany, Dr. R. G. Bhojar Arts, Comm. & Science College, Seloo, Dist. Wardha, Maharashtra. A Voucher number is 09/rgbacscbotany/2024-2025.

Preparation of extract

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

The dried stem of *T. cordifolia* (TCS) was ground into a coarse powder. An ethanolic extract of the drug was initially prepared using a Soxhlet apparatus. The solvent was subsequently recovered through distillation, and the extract was dried using a water bath maintained at 40-50°C. The resultant dried extract of *T. cordifolia* stem (TCSE) exhibited a reddish-brown color, with an approximate yield of 6.15%. The dried extract was stored in an airtight container and refrigerated [4, 5].

GC - MS Analysis:

The GCMS analysis was performed using the GCMS-QP2010 Ultra SHIMADZU, equipped with high-resolution GCMS solution software. The instrument featured an Rxi-5Sil MS Column, a fused silica capillary column with dimensions of 30 m × 0.25 mm ID × 0.25 µm df. The system operated at ionization energy of 70eV for the detection of GCMS results. Helium gas (99.99%) was utilized as the carrier gas, with an injection volume of 2µl. The injector temperature was set at 310°C, and the ion-source temperature was maintained at 230°C. The interphase

temperature was 352°C, and the oven temperature was programmed to initiate at 80°C, increasing at a rate of 0°C/min to 250°C, followed by a hold time of 5 minutes. Subsequently, the temperature was increased at a rate of 20°C/min to 325°C, concluding with a hold time of 13 minutes. Mass spectra were recorded with a solvent cut time of 4 minutes, and the total GCMS running time was 30.00 minutes. The average peak area relative to the total area was compared to determine the relative percentage of each phytoconstituent.

Identification of Components:

Bioactive compounds were identified through the interpretation of mass spectra obtained via GC-MS, utilizing the databases of the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST11) and WILEY 8. The mass spectrum of the unidentified component was compared with the spectra of known components stored in the NIST 11 and WILEY 8 libraries [6]. The names, molecular weights, and molecular formulas of the components of the test materials were systematically listed.

Figure 1: Chromatogram of GC - MS ethanolic stem extract

Table 1: GC-MS analysis of bioactive compounds in ethanol extract of *T. cordifolia* stem

Peak	R. Time	Area%	Height	Molecular formula	Molecular weight (g/mol)	Name
1	10.991	0.54	7557188	C16H34	226	Hexadecane
2	13.400	0.67	3832552	C14H28O2	228	C20H38 acid
3	13.600	0.54	3232115	C20H40	280	9-Eicosene,(E)-
4	13.857	0.66	10267724	C20H38	278	Neophytadiene
5	13.985	0.67	5290790	C15H30O2	242	Pentadecanoic acid

6	14.129	1.12	8172361	C27H44O3	416	Calcitriol
7	14.550	12.15	131779871	C16H32O2	256	n-Hexadecanoicacid
8	14.964	0.38	4485632	C18H34O2	282	OleicAcid
9	15.061	1.72	22426117	C16H32O2	256	n-Hexadecanoicacid
10	15.475	15.48	113416556	C16H30O	238	Z,Z-8,10-Hexadecadien-1-ol
11	15.571	5.54	59819927	C18H36O2	284	Octadecanoicacid
12	15.740	0.48	2924040	C26H54	366	Hexacosane
13	16.360	0.39	3808323	C54H108Br2	914	Tetrapentacontane,1,54-dibromo-
14	16.762	0.35	6042645	C11H17BrO2	260	7-Bromo-3a,6,6-trimethyl-hexahydro-benzofuran-2(3H)-one
15	16.822	0.47	8583720	C18H34O	266	14-Octadecenal
16	16.884	0.56	9213147	C24H20F10O4	562	Sebacicacid,dipentafluorobenzylester
17	17.102	1.34	10318019	C26H52O2	396	2-Ethylbutyricacid,eicosylester
18	17.234	0.70	6818699	C19H38O4	330	Hexadecanoicacid,2-hydroxy-1-(hydroxymethyl)ethylester
19	17.350	2.47	31673916	C15H15F5O2	322	3-Cyclopentylpropionicacid,pentafluorobenzylester
20	17.590	0.91	3823398	C23H44O3	368	Carbonicacid,eicosylvinylester
21	17.724	1.09	10686903	C13H24O	196	Tetrahydroedulan
22	17.854	1.96	13206861	C24H20F10O4	562	Sebacicacid,dipentafluorobenzylester
23	18.147	1.35	8561543	C23H44O3	368	Carbonicacid,eicosylvinylester
24	18.742	0.76	6843253	C22H43NO	337	13-Docosenamide,(Z)-
25	18.909	1.05	8985501	C30H50	410	Squalene
26	19.170	0.53	5206031	C25H46O6	442	Octadecanoicacid,2-(acetyloxy)-1-[(acetyloxy)methyl]ethylester
27	19.225	0.92	11264005	C23H42O6	414	Hexadecanoicacid,2,3-bis(acetyloxy)propylester
28	19.470	0.53	3929162	C16H33I	352	Hexadecane, 1-iodo-
29	19.534	0.72	8211007	C27H56O	396	1-Heptacosanol
30	19.825	0.38	3828124	C24H72O12Si12	888	Tetracosamethyl-cyclododecasiloxane
31	20.790	0.59	3764923	C32H58	442	1,1,6-trimethyl-3-methylene-2-(3,6,10,13,14-pentamethyl-3-et
32	20.980	0.60	2565965	C24H72O12Si12	888	Tetracosamethyl-cyclododecasiloxane
33	21.320	3.64	24205838	C25H44O6	440	9-Octadecenoic acid (Z)-, 2,3-bis(acetyloxy)propyl ester
34	21.402	5.58	48117703	C25H44O6	440	9-Octadecenoic acid (Z)-, 2,3-bis(acetyloxy)propyl ester
35	21.460	4.26	34121010	C27H56O	396	1-Heptacosanol
36	21.710	0.73	3791108	C30H50O2	442	Ergost-5-en-3-ol, acetate, (3.beta.,24R)-
37	21.872	0.73	6119918	C29H50O2	430	dl.-alpha.-Tocopherol
38	23.056	1.68	12126967	C32H52O2	468	9,19-Cycloergost-24(28)-en-3-ol, 4,14-dimethyl-, acetate, (3.b
39	23.424	3.63	21082917	C24H38O3	374	3.beta.-Hydroxy-5-cholen-24-oic acid
40	23.780	2.40	15297716	C29H48O	412	Stigmasterol
41	24.260	0.80	3790592	C27H56O	396	1-Heptacosanol
42	24.410	0.91	6887208	C26H44O4S	452	Methanesulfonic acid, 2-(3-hydroxy-4,4,10,13,14-pentamethyl
43	24.763	8.17	45435849	C29H50O	414	.beta.-Sitosterol
44	25.217	1.38	8966590	C17H28O2	264	(-)-Isolongifolol, acetate
45	25.476	3.04	15888443	C21H36O3	336	Pregnane-3,11,20-triol, (3.alpha., 11.beta., 20.beta.)-
46	25.659	1.86	9856087	C29H46	394	24-Noroleana-3,12-diene

47	26.112	0.87	5479774	C30H50O	426	Lupeol
48	26.520	2.71	12120235	C30H50O	426	Lupeol

Table 2: Pharmacological activity of phytocomponents in ethanolic extract of *T. cordifolia* stem

Name of the compound	Pharmacological activity	References
Hexadecane	Cytotoxicity, Antimicrobial, Antioxidant, Antipyretic, Anthelmintic, Tumour, Bronchitis, Asthma, Tuberculosis, Dyspepsia, Constipation, Anemia, Throat diseases, Elephantiasis, Antidiabetic, Anti-inflammatory, Antidiarrhoeal	[1]
Tetradecanoicacid	Antioxidant, Lubricant, Hypercholesterolemic, Cancer-preventive, Cosmetic	[7]
9-Eicosene,(E)-	Hypotensive effect, antimicrobial property	[8]
Neophytadiene	anxiolytic-like and anticonvulsant activities	[9]
Pentadecanoicacid	anti-inflammatory, anticancer, antifibrotic, antimicrobial, and mTOR-inhibiting activities	[10]
Calcitriol	Neuroinflammation and Reduces Blood-Brain Barrier Disruption and Local Macrophage/ Microglia Activation	[11]
n-Hexadecanoicacid	Antioxidant and antibacterial	[12,13]
OleicAcid	Antioxidant, Antimicrobial, Antifungal, anticonvulsive activity, Anti-atherosclerosis, Anesthetic, Anti-helminthic, Antianxiety, Antibacterial, Antiberiberi, Antibiotic, Anticancer, Anti-convulsion, Anti-diabetic, Anti-diarrheic, Anti-fertility, Anti-gastric, Anti-inflammatory, Anti-obesity, Anti-ulcer, Anti-tuberculosis, Anti-cold, Antihepatotoxic and Anti-viral activity	[14]
Z,Z-8,10-Hexadecadien-1-ol	Not known	
Octadecanoicacid	anti-bacterial and antioxidant drugs.	[15]
Hexacosane	Antimicrobial	[16]
Tetrapentacontane,1,54-dibromo-	Not known	
7-Bromo-3a,6,6-trimethyl-hexahydro-benzofuran-2(3H)-one	Not known	
14-Octadecenal	Not known	
Sebacicacid,dipentafluoro benzylester	Not known	
2-Ethylbutyricacid,eicosylester	Not known	
Hexadecanoicacid,2-hydroxy-1-(hydroxymethyl)ethylester	Antioxidant, Hypocholesterolemic ,Nematicide, Pesticide, Lubricant, Antiandrogenic, Flavor, Hemolytic, 5-Alpha reductase inhibitor	[7]
3-Cyclopentylpropionicacid ,pentafluorobenzylester	Not known	

Carbonicacid,eicosylviny lester	antioxidant activity, bacterial infections	[17]
Tetrahydroedulan	Not known	[6]
13-Docosenamido,(Z)-	Antioxidant,Antimicrobial and cytotoxic activitie	[18]
Squalene	Antibacterial, Antioxidant, Antitumor, Cancer preventive, Immunostimulant, Chemo preventive, Lipoxigenase-inhibitor, Pesticide	[1]
Octadecanoicacid,2-(acetyloxy)-1-[(acetyloxy)methyl]ethyle	Not known	
Hexadecanoicacid,2,3-bis(acetyloxy)propylester	Not known	
Hexadecane, 1-iodo-	Not known	
1-Heptacosanol	Flavouring and fragrance agent, Cholesterol lowering, antimicrobial and Cytotoxicity, antithrombotic	[19]
Tetracosamethyl-cyclododecasiloxane	Hepatoprotective, antispasmodic, antirheumatic	[20]
1,1,6-trimethyl-3-methylene-2-(3,6,10,13,14-pentamethyl-3-et	Not known	
9-Octadecenoic acid (Z)-, 2,3-bis(acetyloxy)propyl ester	Anti-inflammatory	[21]
Ergost-5-en-3-ol, acetate, (3.beta.,24R)-	Not known	
dl.-alpha.-Tocopherol	Antioxidant	[22]
9,19-Cycloergost-24(28)-en-3-ol, 4,14-dimethyl-, acetate, (3.b	Not known	
3.beta.-Hydroxy-5-cholen-24-oic acid	Belongs to the class of bile acids bearing ahydroxyl group. Bile acids facilitate fat absorption	[14]
Stigmasterol	Anti-infammatory, antioxidant, antimicrobial, sedative activity, anticancer, Diuretic, hypoglycemic and thyroid inhibitor, antiarthritic, antiasthama	[8]
Methanesulfonic acid, 2-(3-hydroxy-4,4,10,13,14-pentamethyl	Not known	
beta.-Sitosterol	Antihemorrhagic, Antimyotoxic, Prostate Cancer And Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia,antiurolithiasis	[21, 23, 24, 25]
(-)-Isolongifolol, acetate	Not known	
Pregnane-3,11,20-triol, (3.alpha., 11.beta., 20.beta.)-	Not known	
24-Noroleana-3,12-diene	Hepatotoxicity	[26]
Lupeol	Anti-inflammatory and Anti-cancer	[27]

RESULTS

The GC-MS chromatogram of the ethanolic leaf extract of *T. cordifolia* revealed 48 peaks, indicating the presence of forty-eight compounds (Figure 1). The

active constituents, along with their peaks, retention time (RT), area (%), height, molecular formula, and molecular weight, are detailed in Table 1. Notably, n-Hexadecanoic acid, Z,Z-8,10-Hexadecadien-1-ol, Octadecanoic acid, 9-Octadecenoic acid (Z)-, 2,3-bis(acetyloxy)propyl ester, and beta-Sitosterol exhibited higher peaks in the chromatogram. The compounds identified by GC-MS exhibited various pharmacological activities, as outlined in Table 2.

DISCUSSION

GC-MS analysis identified 48 chemical compounds. Among these, n-hexadecanoic acid (131779871) was the most abundant, whereas tetracosamethylcyclododecasiloxane (2565965) was the least abundant. Notably, n-Hexadecanoic acid exhibits antioxidant and antibacterial activities. In contrast, Z,Z-8,10-Hexadecadien-1-ol has not been reported to have any activity by previous researchers. Octadecanoic acid is known for its antibacterial and antioxidant properties, and 9-Octadecenoic acid (Z)-, 2,3-bis(acetyloxy)propyl ester demonstrates anti-inflammatory properties. Additionally, beta-Sitosterol is associated with antihemorrhagic, antimyotoxic, prostate cancer, benign prostatic hyperplasia, and antiurolithiasis activities, and these five chemical compounds exhibited higher peaks in the chromatogram. Further isolation and characterization of individual phytochemical constituents are warranted to discover novel drugs and their pharmacological activities.

CONCLUSION

The ethanolic leaf extract of *Tinospora cordifolia* comprises 48 distinct chemical compounds, some of which exhibit unique pharmacological activities. These compounds can be individually extracted and utilized in clinical trials to assess their efficacy and facilitate the development of novel drugs from crude sources, such as plants. Additionally, GC-MS analysis of the stem extract will contribute to the database of bioactive products derived from natural drugs.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The first authors would like to express a sincere thank to Rashtrasant Tukadoji Maharaj Memorial

Fellowship Nagpur University, Nagpur for providing the financial assistance.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

Authors have no any conflict of interest.

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HOW TO CITE: N. D. Chahande, V. N. Patil* and R. O. Ganjiwale, GC-MS Analysis of Bioactive Compounds from Ethanolic Stem Extract of *Tinospora Cordifolia* and Their Pharmacological Activities, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, 1 (10), 244-251. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17333183>

